

A STUDY OF SPIRITUAL INTELLIGENCE AMONG B.Ed STUDENTS

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Abstract:

The major aim of the study was to find out spiritual intelligence of B.Ed students. Total sample of 240 subjects were taken for this study. The sample comprises of 123 male and 117 female B.Ed students were selected using non probability purposive sampling technique. Descriptive analysis of the data was done to obtain Mean and Standard Deviation. Independent sample t-test and F test was used to find out the significant difference between the sub samples such as gender, locality of institution, mode of management, degree obtained, religion, year of study and type of family. The findings of the study concluded that there is no significant difference on spiritual intelligence between gender, locality of institution, mode of management, degree obtained, religion, year of study and type of family of B.Ed students.

Introduction:

Spirituality is derived from the Latin word "Spirare" meaning to breathe. Spirituality is inherent aspect of human nature and essence of our existence so it draws attention of many theorists as the source of all thoughts, feelings, values and behavior. The field of psychology has shown the tendency towards the spiritual dimensions and wide horizons for extended research has spread that can reflect the profound influence of spiritual forces on the human body and mind and makes clear the importance of spiritual intelligence. Some research studies have paid to the effect of spirituality on the overall health of the individuals. Mental health professionals have recognized the power of spiritual intelligence, some of which are defined as capacity to feel, understand and present the highest part of themselves, others and the world around.

Spiritual Intelligence:

According to Webster's dictionary the word "Spirit" defines as "the animating or vital principle: that which gives life to the physical organism in contrast to its material elements: the breath of life". Wigglesworth et al., (2012) defines spiritual intelligence as "the ability to behave with wisdom and compassion, while maintaining inner and outer peace, regardless of the situation". Vaughan (2002) stated that the spiritual intelligence is the consequence of the highest level of individual growth in the fields of cognition, meaning attainment, transcendental and moral communication. Zohar and Marshal (2000) believe that spiritual intelligence facilitates association between cause and emotion, as well as, body and mind and builds a supportive force for growth and rising. It provides an active, unity, and meaningful centre for soul to help people think profoundly about essential subjects and try to solve their daily problems.

- ✓ Spiritual intelligence emphasizes on life with purpose and meaning. This could encourage students to find hope and joy in living in contrast to escapism.
- ✓ An emphasis on community - an understanding that we need and must care for each other. This could offset the reigning me attitudes.
- ✓ Spiritual Intelligence imbibes the quest for wisdom of life. This could lend a noble vision to study, with every discipline of knowledge fostering an ethic for life.
- ✓ All great spiritual movements teach justice for all and compassion for the needy. This suggests education in critical consciousness and commitment to social service and transformation.
- ✓ All spiritualities also are convinced that the person is essentially spiritual, that the human vocation is to live in "right relationship" with oneself, others, and creation. Such values seem distant from the society we live in.

Spiritual intelligence, as defined by researchers, is strongly connected to the fulfillment of a human being's profound need – to feel that everything has a meaning, a purpose. It is the intelligence that makes us whole and renders our integrity. It is the intelligence of the soul, the profound self-intelligence. It is the intelligence that makes us ask ourselves fundamental, existential questions and overcome the boundaries we were used to.

Aim:

The aim of the present study was to study the spiritual intelligence among B.Ed students.

Sample:

Total sample of 240 subjects were taken for this study. The sample comprises of 123 male and 117 female B.Ed students. Data was collected from Vellore district.

Description of Tool:

The scale was developed following the Likert’s method. For scoring the scale, a score of 5,4,3,2, and 1 was given to category. The sum of the scores of all the statements constituted the total score of the scale. The maximum and minimum scores, which the students may score on SI, will be 600 and 120 respectively. There are five response categories (Strongly agree), (Agree), (Uncertain), (Disagree) and (Strongly disagree) for each of the 120 items.

Objectives:

- ✓ To study the significant difference between gender of B.Ed students score towards spiritual intelligence.
- ✓ To study the significant difference between locality of institution of B.Ed students score towards spiritual intelligence.
- ✓ To study the significant difference between mode of management of B.Ed students score towards spiritual intelligence.
- ✓ To study the significant difference between degree obtained of B.Ed students score towards spiritual intelligence.
- ✓ To study the significant difference between religion of B.Ed students score towards spiritual intelligence.
- ✓ To study the significant difference between year of study of B.Ed students score towards spiritual intelligence.
- ✓ To study the significant difference between type of family of B.Ed students score towards spiritual intelligence.

Hypotheses of the Study:

- ✓ There is no significant difference between gender of B.Ed students score towards spiritual intelligence.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between locality of institution of B.Ed students score towards spiritual intelligence.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between mode of management of B.Ed students score towards spiritual intelligence.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between degree obtained of B.Ed students score towards spiritual intelligence.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between religion of B.Ed students score towards spiritual intelligence.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between year of study of B.Ed students score towards spiritual intelligence.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between type of family of B.Ed students score towards spiritual intelligence.

Analysis of Data:

Gender and Spiritual Intelligence:

Table 1: Comparison of gender of B.Ed students on spiritual intelligence

Gender	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ Value
Male	123	384.13	36.80	0.219 NS
Female	117	382.99	44.04	

It is evident from the Table 1; the calculated ‘t’ value is 0.219, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between male and female B.Ed Students with respect to their spiritual intelligence.

Locality of institution and Spiritual Intelligence:

Table 2: Comparison of locality of institution of B.Ed students on Spiritual Intelligence

Locality of institution	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ Value
Rural	105	387.80	47.48	0.009
Urban	135	380.28	33.74	NS

It is evident from the Table 2; the calculated ‘t’ value is 0.009, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between rural and urban B.Ed Students with respect to their spiritual intelligence.

Mode of Management and Spiritual Intelligence:

Table 3: Comparison of mode of management of B.Ed students on spiritual intelligence

Mode of Management	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ Value
Government	145	389.57	37.63	0.531 NS
Self-finance	95	374.42	42.92	

It is evident from the Table 3; the calculated 't' value is 0.531, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between Government and Self-finance B.Ed Students with respect to their spiritual intelligence.

Degree Obtained and Spiritual Intelligence:

Table 4: Comparison of degree obtained of B.Ed students on spiritual intelligence

Degree Obtained	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value
Between Groups	2573.49	1286.74	2	0.786 NS
Within Groups	387815.00	1636.35	237	
Total	390388.49		239	

It is evident from the Table 4; the calculated 'F' value is 0.786, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of Degree Obtained with respect to their Spiritual intelligence of B.Ed students.

Religion and Spiritual Intelligence:

Table 5: Comparison of religion of B.Ed students on spiritual intelligence

Religion	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value
Between Groups	22156.17	11078.08	2	7.130 NS
Within Groups	368232.32	1553.72	237	
Total	390388.49		239	

It is evident from the Table 5; the calculated 'F' value is 7.130, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of Religion with respect to their Spiritual intelligence of B.Ed students.

Year of Study and Spiritual Intelligence:

Table 6: Comparison of year of study of B.Ed students on spiritual intelligence

Year of Study	N	Mean	SD	't' Value
I st	75	391.65	38.93	0.476 NS
II nd	165	373.90	40.65	

It is evident from the Table 6; the calculated 't' value is 0.476, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between Ist and IInd B.Ed Students with respect to their Spiritual intelligence.

Type of Family and Spiritual Intelligence:

Table 7: Comparison of type of family of B.Ed students on spiritual intelligence

Type of Family	N	Mean	SD	't' Value
Nuclear	112	386.18	39.55	0.935 NS
Joint	128	381.29	41.17	

It is evident from the Table 7; the calculated 't' value is 0.935, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between Nuclear and Joint B.Ed Students with respect to their Spiritual intelligence.

Major Findings of the Study:

- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between male and female B.Ed Students with respect to their spiritual intelligence.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between rural and urban B.Ed Students with respect to their spiritual intelligence.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between Government and Self-finance B.Ed Students with respect to their spiritual intelligence.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of Degree Obtained with respect to their Spiritual intelligence of B.Ed students.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of Religion with respect to their Spiritual intelligence of B.Ed students.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between Ist and IInd B.Ed Students with respect to their Spiritual intelligence.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between Nuclear and Joint B.Ed Students with respect to their Spiritual intelligence.

Conclusion:

Teachers with high spiritual intelligence have an ability to reframe, and to see things in a wider context. This will embrace their holistic thinking and engages the whole person - teaching students to think critically and

creatively for themselves. Through high spiritual intelligence the effectiveness of student teachers can be enhanced and that will enable them to teach with seeing larger patterns and relationships in their personal and professional life. Spiritual Intelligence is the central part of all types of intelligence, the core of intelligences, which has a coordinating role in this system. It is the intelligence situated in a profound part of the being, connected to the wisdom beyond the ego. Due to spiritual intelligence, we have access to our transcendent dimension. It is the intelligence with the aid of which we do not only acknowledge the existent values, but we also discover new ones in a creative way.

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